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Research Article

AESTHETICS IN ECOLOGICAL CULTUREI.V. Abdrashitova¹, A.B Abdrashitova², R.M. Safina², A.E. Abdrashitov².¹Kazan (Volga region) Federal University, 18 Kremlevskaya St, Kazan 420008, Russia;²Federal State Budgetary Educational Institution of Higher Education Kazan State Medical University of the Ministry of Healthcare of Russia, 49 Butlerov St, Kazan 420012, Russia.**Article Received:** April 2019**Accepted:** May 2019**Published:** June 2019

Annotation: *This article contains information about the formation of environmental culture of students in the process of extracurricular activities. The model for the pedagogical experiment is presented, the information saturation of blocks and modules is revealed, the dynamics of the conducted ecological and educational project is indicated.*

Keywords: *Ecological Culture, Pedagogical Experiment, Ecological Aesthetics.*

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INTRODUCTION:

A fundamentally important characteristic of our time is the sharp aggravation of global, regional and local environmental problems. The successful solution of the problem cannot be limited to the adoption of measures of economic or scientific and technical content. The fair statement of Professor S. I. Glazychev that a new system of values, in the creation of which a special role belongs to environmental education, should replace the nature-conquering view of the world, sounds especially important today [1,2].

The school has opportunities for environmental education in the lessons of the biological cycle, but pedagogical research shows that within the time limit it is impossible to form an environmental culture of the individual. Modern students have a low level of environmental knowledge and value judgments about the natural world, which in the future will inevitably affect the quality of adaptation to the social environment, the ability to consciously carry out natural activities.

Thus, we came to the conclusion that it is necessary to develop a system of ecological and pedagogical activities that will allow students to develop a strong interest in the natural world on the basis of basic knowledge, skills and abilities obtained in the lessons of the biological cycle and in the process of extracurricular activities to reassess the value of nature. On the basis of the development of environmental interest, aesthetic attitude will be formed environmental knowledge, skills, contributing to the formation of environmental culture of students.

"Environmental culture – the level of development of General culture characterized by awareness of the intrinsic value of the natural world and humans as part of nature, developed a need for responsible, foreseen, appropriate activities based on moral and aesthetic values and the perception of the natural environment, leading to the humane determination of conformity and harmony between environmental needs moral and aesthetically educated person with the capabilities of the natural world, leading to convergence of nature and culture, i.e. econosphere".

Aesthetics as a component of ecological culture contributes to the birth of aesthetic feelings, experiences and relationships, which are expressed in a reasonable creative use of its wealth. Aesthetic values of nature actualize the creative development of personality. Aesthetic creativity spiritually enriches the personality and directs its activity on augmentation of aesthetic riches of the natural world

[3,4].

Environmental culture of students, formed on the basis of aesthetic qualities will develop the ability of self-regulation: the ability to organize their activities, coordinating it with the efforts of others; predict the results of their activities in nature; organize environmental activities [5].

Research objective: Theoretical justification and practical realization of pedagogical activity on formation of ecological culture of the person on the basis of an aesthetic component.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks are put forward: General education: to learn the basic environmental concepts, to highlight the severity of environmental problems associated with pollution of the environment, to identify possible ways to solve them; to reveal the trends of aesthetic education of students on the basis of studying the art of landscape design.

Developing: to form the ability to collect and analyze environmental information, to draw conclusions, generalizations and conclusions about the state of nature, to develop the ability of aesthetic evaluation of natural phenomena from the standpoint of artistic taste, to acquire the skills of landscape design and work with natural material.

Educational: to form a moral and aesthetic attitude to nature, to develop a sense of duty and responsibility in unity with a sense of admiration for the beauty of the natural world, to cultivate the need for aesthetic communication with nature through creative activity.

For formation of ecological culture of pupils the method of modeling of V. A. shtoff Was applied. Experimental study of the model is to transfer the simulation results to a natural object.

"Model of formation of ecological culture of pupils in the process of extracurricular activities" is presented by motivational, creative, educational blocks.

Motivational block involves the development of the motivational sphere of personality, ie, motivational forces for the formation of the aesthetic component of environmental culture, based on knowledge, skills obtained in the study of subjects of the biological cycle in the process of extracurricular activities. The motivational block includes activities that carry information from the field of ecology, botany and physiology of plants, which will not only deepen knowledge, but also form the ideological space,

views, beliefs, interest, sustainable motivation and influence the development of the individual as a whole, creating a holistic image of the natural world, revealing the concept of "man - nature".

The creative block includes lectures, laboratory and practical classes of ecological and aesthetic orientation, contributing to the manifestation and development of aesthetic properties of the person. It is here that students will achieve the strength of assimilation of the studied material and acquire the necessary skills, abilities, experience with natural material (drawing up design projects, breeding plants and caring for them), learn how to protect projects, analyze and formulate conclusions that are born after discussing the results and jointly made decisions. Such work gives rise to emotional perception of what is happening, is remembered for a long time and brings satisfaction.

The educational block contains special material (lectures, practical classes, watching videos, issuing wall Newspapers, preparing abstracts, etc.), contributing to the manifestation of environmental knowledge, the development and formation of aesthetic properties of the individual, skills in the classroom of a creative nature, as well as research activities of students. In addition, the participants of the environmental circle in this part of the program transfer their knowledge to primary school students. Thus, they are not only brought up themselves, but also learn to educate younger students. This block is supposed to assimilate knowledge, skills, orienting students to the organization of environmental work in the school in order to form an environmental culture of the individual and the development of creative abilities.

MATERIAL AND RESEARCH METHODS:

The pedagogical experiment was conducted in the educational space of the school № 41 in Kazan, in the process of extracurricular activities. 52 pupils of the fifth-eighth grades participated in the program, 35 of them – control group, 17 - experimental group. Pedagogical experiment consisted of summative, formative and diagnostic stages. As part of the program was developed "Model of formation of the aesthetic component of environmental culture of students."

RESULTS:

The training module creates the necessary theoretical basis in the field of ecology, aesthetics and landscape design.

The training module of the motivational block

includes lectures and talks "Introduction to ecology", "History of landscape design", "Basic elements of landscape design", demonstration of videos "Landscape design", "Famous gardens of Europe", excursion to the greenhouse of the Kazan zoo Botanical garden. In the creative block contains lecture material "the Value of plants in human life", "Trees. Functions of trees in the garden", "Tree-shrub groups", "flower Beds. Flower garden projects". The training module of the educational unit includes lectures and talks "Environmental education of students", "Aesthetics of natural objects", "Save nature for ourselves and future generations".

These activities deepen students' knowledge about the basic environmental concepts, modern environmental problems and ways to overcome them, reveal the relationship of ecology and aesthetics, develop aesthetic consciousness and form the theoretical basis necessary for the further development of the aesthetic component of environmental culture.

The module includes practical exercises formative skills, experience with natural materials, as well as translating the ecological knowledge to practical activities.

The practical module of the motivational block includes individual work on the development of the design project of the cottage, group work of the design project of the school site and the project of the flower bed in the Park "Millennium". The practical module of the creative block is full of laboratory and practical classes, "plant Planting and care for them", "Transplanting and reproduction of indoor plants", "Composition of indoor plants". The practical module of the educational unit contains activities for primary school students conducted by high school students: "Nature is our home", design of the wall newspaper "Green rescuers of our planet", quiz "we Bring beauty to our garden".

These works in the framework of the practical module will allow students to summarize all the material learned in the classroom of the training unit and apply them in practice, as well as to gain skills in landscape design. Group and collective work contribute to the emergence of team spirit in the environmental circle. The execution of tasks on the compilation of landscape design projects forms the aesthetic experience of the development of natural spaces, develops the aesthetic taste, nourishes work in a mug with a creative component.

The research module includes tasks aimed at search

activity – selection of information on a given topic and preparation of the presentation of their own scientific and practical work.

The research module of the motivational block involves the preparation and report of essays "History of landscape design", "landscape architecture", "Small architectural forms", "Garden design", "Variety of colors"; creative block - includes the preparation and presentation of essays "Variety of indoor plants", "light-Loving, shade-loving plants", "Indoor plants – care, reproduction", "Style placement of indoor flowers". The research module of the educational unit contains activities on the aesthetics of the natural world, which high school students spend for primary school students (jointly explore and establish a harmonious proportionality of wildlife on the principle of the Golden section) and organize preparations for the reporting conference.

During the implementation of the research module, students accumulate experience with literary sources, form an environmental interest in the natural world and aesthetic attitude to nature.

The control module makes it possible to assess the level of environmental education of students, to ensure the effectiveness of the proposed methods of formation of environmental culture of students, to determine the measures of correction and improvement of the system and to make statistical calculations.

At the level of the control module in the motivational, creative and educational blocks are held debates at the round table "Environmental aesthetics", the reporting conference of the environmental circle "Beauty will save the world", diagnosing testing and statistical processing of data of pedagogical experiment.

The control module reveals not only the level of acquired knowledge and skills in the process of pedagogical experiment, but also determines the dynamics of qualitative changes in the aesthetic consciousness of students.

At the end of the formative experiment, a control examination of the participants of the experimental and control groups was conducted in order to identify the dynamics of the levels of formation of aesthetic education of students. The changes in the structure of the aesthetic consciousness of the individual are noted. Dynamics is observed in the formation of aesthetic qualities of the person. In communication and the study of the nature of students' increased

ability to perceive, to feel, to experience and discover new aesthetic potential of nature. This ability allowed to develop an interest in the aesthetic phenomena of nature, became the basis of a creative attitude to nature. The ability of aesthetic judgment about nature, the ability of reasonable evaluation of natural aesthetic phenomena and formed new forms of interaction.

CONCLUSIONS:

The results allow us to conclude that the pedagogical experiment on the formation of the aesthetic component of the environmental culture of students in the process of extracurricular activities was successful, has a positive dynamics and can be used in educational institutions in the process of environmental education of students.

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